

THE ROLE OF EXERCISES AND ASSIGNMENTS IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEAKING COMPETENCES THROUGH WORKING ON TEXT FOR FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents and analyzes the views of methodologists, educators and psychologists on exercises and tasks for future primary school teachers aimed at developing students' speech competencies through working with texts, scientific concepts, contextual learning and the theoretical foundations of pedagogical tools..

The basis of the reforms being implemented at the educational levels today is to educate the younger generation, students, to the level of a well-educated, capable, capable, fluent, mature and well-rounded person. As our President Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized, "We will mobilize all the forces and capabilities of our state and society so that our youth, having high intellectual and spiritual potential who think independently, can become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field in the world, can mature and be happy." There is ancient wisdom in the thoughts.

In the context of the new Uzbekistan, which is developing rapidly through the implementation of high-level reforms, it has been determined that one of the main tasks is to raise young students who are the foundation of our future, who think freely and independently, speak fluently, have a creative approach, deeply master modern knowledge, and act as enthusiastic children for the fate of their homeland. The role of language education in educating young people is incomparable. Conducting lessons at a high level, introducing modern pedagogical technologies into the lesson, developing new teaching methods, teachers working on themselves, and keeping up with the times have become the main tasks facing educators, mature specialists, and teachers.

In recent years, favorable conditions and opportunities have been created in primary education to develop the speech competencies of primary school students, to ensure that subjects of education acquire strong knowledge and develop potential. It is important for primary school science teachers to effectively use these opportunities and conditions to organize lessons using modern technologies and innovative methods. In native language and reading literacy classes, the primary source for primary school students to understand the

topic is the textbook, while the second is the text, subtext exercises and tasks. In primary education, each exercise included in the content of the curriculum and textbooks serves as educational material to strengthen the knowledge, skills and competencies of primary school students related to the development of their speech competencies. I.M. Podgaetskaya thinks as follows about the implementation of exercises and tasks: "... methodologically, interest is understood as an emotional attitude that arouses in students a desire to learn the knowledge being learned in the subject and stimulates enthusiasm for this subject. From the outside, this attitude is manifested in diligence and curiosity."¹. As a result of completing the exercises, elementary school students will have the opportunity to consciously assimilate the knowledge they have acquired and apply it to practical activities necessary when working with text.

It is worth noting that in order to develop the speech competencies of primary school students, serious attention should be paid to the preparation of exercises and tasks. The idea of organizing exercises in the textbook "Didactics of the Mother Tongue", compiled under the leadership of O. Rozikov, is relevant. "In the process of preparing educational tasks for practice, the following work is carried out.

Integrativeness of exercises and tasks in developing students' speech competencies through work on text for future primary school teachers

A. Determine the number of heuristic, adaptive, non-adaptive, alternative learning tasks for speech forms;

B. Take into account the creative and memorization activities of students in the system of learning tasks being developed;

C. Determine the type of tasks according to the content of the educational material. In the process of developing tasks, the focus should be on the development of speech and thinking, while taking into account the consolidation of the topic"².

In addition to the mastery of educational material on the topic by primary school students, the development of creativity and independent thinking gives a positive result and increases the effectiveness of the lesson. The use of grammatical, speech, and special exercises

¹ Подгаецкая И.М. Воспитание учащихся интереса к изучению русского языка. –Т.: Просвещение, 1985. –208с

² Roziqov O.R v.b. Ona tili didaktikasi. – Т.:Yangi asr avlodi, 2005. –626

in textbooks taught in primary school is also effective in increasing the effectiveness of the lesson. According to H. Bakiyeva, "In order for students to acquire the skills of expressing their thoughts correctly and perfectly, the teacher should regularly organize special exercises that eliminate speech defects and enrich speech with lexical units"³.

Special exercises play an important role in the formation of knowledge and skills of primary school students, in eliminating errors and shortcomings. Such exercises include non-standard exercises and tasks. Independent educational tasks of a non-standard nature are tasks whose method of completion is unknown to the student and are based on search, requiring the application of existing knowledge in non-similar conditions. Non-standard exercises and tasks are distinguished by the fact that they serve to increase speech competence and expand knowledge as a result of students' search in the learning process.

By working on the text, future primary school teachers develop students' speech competencies by completing exercises and tasks, which increases their ability to speak, think, and reflect, which in turn affects the development of their logical thinking.

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